

A GLOBAL LOCAL METHOD FOR ANALYSIS OF THICK COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

In this paper a global-local method for analysis of thick composite laminates is presented. This method involves using an effective modulus theory to obtain the effective stress field in the laminate and then recovering the local stress field in each layer from the global-local relationships in the 3-D effective modulus theory. Through the illustration of a half space laminated solid with a load distributed uniformly over a strip, the validity of the global-local method is examined.

INTRODUCTION

Thick laminates consist of large numbers of laminae. Hence, it is impractical to perform stress analysis by considering each individual lamina. Pagano [1] employed the longwave approach to derive effective elastic moduli for anisotropic laminates. Instead of assuming the existence of periodic structuring through the laminate thickness, he considered a representative volume which contains the whole thickness of the laminate. Because of the finite thickness, moment effects were also included in the "stress-strain" relations.

Recently, Sun and Li [2] derived explicit expressions of effective elastic constants for thick laminates consisting of large numbers of a repeating sublaminar (the typical cell). The thickness of the typical sublaminar was assumed to be small as compared with the total laminate thickness, and the laminate was modeled as a three-dimensional homogeneous anisotropic solid whose effective moduli are derived from a representative volume -- the typical sublaminar. The sublaminar was evaluated using constant stress and constant strain assumptions for its six independent modes of deformation.

In this paper, the effective modulus modes for thick laminates is evaluated for problems in which the characteristic length of deformation may be comparable to the thickness of the typical sublaminar. The laminate is first regarded as a homogeneous anisotropic solid and the effective stress and strain fields are determined. A procedure to recover the stresses in each lamina from the effective stress and strain fields is developed. These solutions are then compared with finite element solutions.

THE GLOBAL SOLUTION

Consider the half-space of a composite laminate consisting of periodic laminae subject to a constant load q as shown in Fig. 1. The load is applied between $-a \leq x \leq a$ and is uniform in the z -direction. Thus, the problem can be considered a generalized plane strain problem.

For simplicity, we consider only balanced laminates (with respect to z -axis). Thus, the effective modulus model for the laminate becomes orthotropic with the principal material axes parallel to the coordinate axes. The stress-strain relations for the effective orthotropic continuum are given by

Fig. 1 Coordinate system and schematic finite element mesh

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \bar{\sigma}_{xx} \\ \bar{\sigma}_{yy} \\ \bar{\sigma}_{zz} \\ \bar{\sigma}_{yz} \\ \bar{\sigma}_{xz} \\ \bar{\sigma}_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{C}_{11} & \bar{C}_{12} & \bar{C}_{13} & & & \\ \bar{C}_{12} & \bar{C}_{22} & \bar{C}_{23} & & & \\ \bar{C}_{13} & \bar{C}_{23} & \bar{C}_{33} & & & \\ & & & \bar{C}_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ & & & 0 & \bar{C}_{55} & 0 \\ & & & 0 & 0 & \bar{C}_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \bar{\epsilon}_{xx} \\ \bar{\epsilon}_{yy} \\ \bar{\epsilon}_{zz} \\ \bar{\gamma}_{yz} \\ \bar{\gamma}_{xz} \\ \bar{\gamma}_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where $\bar{\sigma}_{ij}$ and $\bar{\epsilon}_{ij}$ are the effective (average) stresses and strains, respectively, and \bar{C}_{ij} are the effective moduli which were derived by Sun and Li [2].

The solution for the half-space problem is given by Lekhnitskii [3]. We have

$$\bar{\sigma}_{xx} = 2\text{Re} \left\{ \frac{\mu_1 \mu_2 q}{2\pi i (\mu_1 - \mu_2)} \left[\mu_1 [\ln(a-z_1) - \ln(-a-z_1)] + \mu_2 [\ln(a-z_2) - \ln(-a-z_2)] \right] \right\} \quad (2)$$

$$\bar{\sigma}_{yy} = 2\text{Re} \left\{ \frac{q}{2\pi i (\mu_1 - \mu_2)} \left[\mu_2 [\ln(a-z_1) - \ln(-a-z_1)] + \mu_1 [\ln(a-z_2) - \ln(-a-z_2)] \right] \right\} \quad (3)$$

$$\bar{\sigma}_{xy} = -2\text{Re} \left\{ \frac{\mu_1 \mu_2 q}{2\pi i (\mu_1 - \mu_2)} \left[[\ln(a-z_1) - \ln(-a-z_1)] + [\ln(a-z_2) - \ln(-a-z_2)] \right] \right\} \quad (4)$$

$$\bar{\sigma}_{zz} = -\frac{1}{\bar{S}_{33}} (\bar{S}_{13} \bar{\sigma}_{xx} + \bar{S}_{23} \bar{\sigma}_{yy}) \quad (5)$$

$$\bar{\sigma}_{yz} = \bar{\sigma}_{xz} = 0 \quad (6)$$

where $\text{Re} \{ \}$ indicates the real part of the complex function in $\{ \}$. In Eqs. (2-6), \bar{S}_{ij} are the effective compliances, i.e.,

$$[\bar{S}] = [\bar{C}]^{-1} \quad (7)$$

μ_k ($k = 1, 2$) and their respective complex conjugates are the complex roots of the characteristic equation

$$\beta_{11}\mu^4 + (2\beta_{12} + \beta_{66})\mu^2 + \beta_{22} = 0 \quad (8)$$

and

$$z_k = x + \mu_k y, \quad k = 1, 2 \quad (9)$$

In Eq. (8), the reduced compliances β_{ij} are given by

$$\beta_{ij} = \bar{S}_{ij} - \bar{S}_{i3}\bar{S}_{j3}/\bar{S}_{33} \quad (10)$$

The corresponding effective strains $\bar{\epsilon}_{ij}$ can be obtained from the inverse relations of Eq. (1).

THE LOCAL SOLUTION

The stresses and strains in the individual laminas are recovered from the basic assumptions regarding the basic deformations in the typical sublaminat. In [1], the following assumptions were made:

$$\sigma_{yy}^k = \bar{\sigma}_{yy}, \quad \sigma_{yz}^k = \bar{\sigma}_{yz}, \quad \sigma_{xy}^k = \bar{\sigma}_{xy} \quad (11)$$

$$\epsilon_{xx}^k = \bar{\epsilon}_{xx}, \quad \epsilon_{zz}^k = \bar{\epsilon}_{zz}, \quad \gamma_{xz}^k = \bar{\gamma}_{xz} \quad (12)$$

where superscript k indicates any lamina in the sublaminat. Thus, only σ_{xx}^k , σ_{zz}^k , and σ_{xz}^k need to be related to the effective stresses or effective strains.

With respect to the coordinate system shown in Fig. 1, the stress-strain relations in each lamina are given by [1]

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{xx}^k &= C_{11}^k \epsilon_{xx}^k + C_{12}^k \epsilon_{yy}^k + C_{13}^k \epsilon_{zz}^k + C_{15}^k \gamma_{xz}^k \\ \sigma_{yy}^k &= C_{12}^k \epsilon_{xx}^k + C_{22}^k \epsilon_{yy}^k + C_{23}^k \epsilon_{zz}^k + C_{25}^k \gamma_{xz}^k \\ \sigma_{zz}^k &= C_{13}^k \epsilon_{xx}^k + C_{23}^k \epsilon_{yy}^k + C_{33}^k \epsilon_{zz}^k + C_{35}^k \gamma_{xz}^k \\ \sigma_{yz}^k &= C_{44}^k \gamma_{yz}^k + C_{46}^k \gamma_{xy}^k \\ \sigma_{xz}^k &= C_{15}^k \epsilon_{xx}^k + C_{25}^k \epsilon_{yy}^k + C_{35}^k \epsilon_{zz}^k + C_{55}^k \gamma_{xz}^k \\ \sigma_{xy}^k &= C_{46}^k \gamma_{yz}^k + C_{66}^k \gamma_{xy}^k \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Using Eqs. (11-12) and rearranging the equations in (13), we obtain

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{xx}^k \\ \sigma_{zz}^k \\ \sigma_{xz}^k \end{Bmatrix} = [A] \begin{Bmatrix} \bar{\epsilon}_{xx} \\ \bar{\epsilon}_{zz} \\ \bar{\gamma}_{xz} \end{Bmatrix} + [B] \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_{yy}^k \\ \gamma_{yz}^k \\ \gamma_{xy}^k \end{Bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \bar{\sigma}_{yy} \\ \bar{\sigma}_{yz} \\ \bar{\sigma}_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = [D] \begin{Bmatrix} \bar{\epsilon}_{xx} \\ \bar{\epsilon}_{zz} \\ \bar{\gamma}_{xz} \end{Bmatrix} + [E] \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_{yy}^k \\ \gamma_{yz}^k \\ \gamma_{xy}^k \end{Bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

Solving Eqs. (14-15), we obtain

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{xx}^k \\ \sigma_{zz}^k \\ \sigma_{xz}^k \end{Bmatrix} = ([A] - [E]^{-1} [D]) \begin{Bmatrix} \bar{\epsilon}_{xx} \\ \bar{\epsilon}_{zz} \\ \bar{\gamma}_{xz} \end{Bmatrix} + [B] [E]^{-1} \begin{Bmatrix} \bar{\sigma}_{yy} \\ \bar{\sigma}_{yz} \\ \bar{\sigma}_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

for the generalized plane strain case, $\bar{\epsilon}_{zz} = 0$. In addition, if the effective medium is orthotropic with the major axes parallel to the coordinate system, then a pure plane strain case results; i.e., $\bar{\gamma}_{xz} = \bar{\gamma}_{yz} = 0$. Thus, Eq. (16) can be simplified to

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{xx}^k &= (C_{11}^k - \frac{C_{12}^k C_{12}^k}{C_{22}^k}) \bar{\epsilon}_{xx} + \frac{C_{12}^k}{C_{22}^k} \bar{\sigma}_{yy} \\ \sigma_{zz}^k &= (C_{13}^k - \frac{C_{12}^k C_{23}^k}{C_{23}^k}) \bar{\epsilon}_{xx} + \frac{C_{23}^k}{C_{22}^k} \bar{\sigma}_{yy} \\ \sigma_{xz}^k &= (C_{15}^k - \frac{C_{12}^k C_{25}^k}{C_{25}^k}) \bar{\epsilon}_{xx} + \frac{C_{25}^k}{C_{22}^k} \bar{\sigma}_{yy} \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

Equation (17) together with (11) give the complete stresses in any lamina.

For sublaminates of the $[\pm\theta]$ type, we have [1]

$$C_{11}^k = \bar{C}_{11} \quad , \quad C_{12}^k = \bar{C}_{12} \quad , \quad C_{22}^k = \bar{C}_{22} \quad , \quad C_{23}^k = \bar{C}_{23} \quad (18)$$

Consequently,

$$\sigma_{xx}^k = \bar{\sigma}_{xx} \quad , \quad \sigma_{zz}^k = \bar{\sigma}_{zz} \quad (19)$$

Thus, only σ_{xz}^k differs from the effective value.

NUMERICAL RESULTS

The laminates considered in the numerical examples are $[0/90]_{250}$ and $[45/-45]_{250}$ of AS4/3501-6 graphite/epoxy composite. The 0° -direction is parallel to the z-axis, and the fiber orientation is measured from the z-axis toward the x-axis, see Fig. 1.

The dimensions of the laminate are shown in Fig. 1. A state of plane strain parallel to x-y plane is assumed. The region of the applied pressure q is taken to be very small as compared with other dimensions of the laminate (i.e., $a \ll h$), in order to simulate the half-space problem considered in the previous sections.

The elastic moduli of the composite are given by

$$\begin{aligned} E_1 &= 138 \text{ GPa} \quad , \quad E_2 = E_3 = 10 \text{ GPa} \\ G_{12} = G &= 13 = 5.5 \text{ GPa} \quad , \quad G_{23} = 3.45 \text{ GPa} \\ \nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = \nu_{23} &= 0.29 \end{aligned}$$

The ply thickness is $t = 0.13$ mm.

An eight-noded isoparametric plane strain finite element is used to model the laminate. The finite element mesh is shown in Fig. 1. Near the applied load, finer meshes are used. Specifically, 4 elements through the thickness are used for the top three laminas, two elements are used for the subsequent nine laminas, and larger elements are used for regions at greater distances from the applied load. The total number of elements used is 2070.

Figures 2-7 present nondimensional stress distributions in the thickness direction at $x/t = 0.05$ for $a/t = 1$ and 10. For the case $a/t = 10$ the area of load application is substantially larger than the ply thickness; the effective modulus solution is excellent even at locations near the applied load. When a is comparable to the ply thickness, as in the case $a/t = 1$, the solution for σ_{xx} is seen to deviate from the finite element solution. This discrepancy is more noticeable in the $[0/90]_{250}$ laminate. Nevertheless, at distances about 10 plies away from the top surface, the effective modulus solution for the $[0/90]_{250}$ laminate starts to converge to the finite element solution. For the $[45/-45]_{250}$ laminate, the effective modulus solution for σ_{xx} converges to the finite element solution within a couple of plies.

CONCLUSION

A 3-D effective modulus model has been employed to perform stress analysis in thick laminates subjected to load applied in a small region. A procedure was introduced to recover local stresses in the laminas from the effective modulus solution. It was demonstrated that if the area of applied load is greater (say 10 times) than the ply thickness, then the effective modulus model could yield excellent solutions in stresses.

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Fig. 2 Distribution of σ_{yy}/q along $x/t = 0.05$ in the $[0/90]_{250}$ laminate for $a/t = 1$.

Fig. 3 Distribution of σ_{yy}/q along $x/t = 0.05$ in the $[0/90]_{250}$ laminate for $a/t = 10$.

Fig. 4 Distribution of σ_{xx}/q along $x/t = 0.05$ in the $[0/90]_{250}$ laminate for $a/t = 1$.

Fig. 5 Distribution of σ_{xx}/q along $x/t = 0.05$ in the $[0/90]_{250}$ laminate for $a/t = 10$.

Fig. 6 Distribution of σ_{xx}/q along $x/t = 0.05$ in the $[45/-45]_{250}$ laminate for $a/t = 1$.

Fig. 7 Distribution of σ_{xx}/q along $x/t = 0.05$ in the $[45/-45]_{250}$ laminate for $a/t = 10$.